

Power of Mother's Breastfeeding: Nature's holistic gift for Neonates *Dr. Nagaveni NB

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It is well known fact that breastfeeding is an important integral part in the life of a woman and a new born baby as it represents the 'God given first gift' from the mother to the baby. In one original research, authors have made a sincere effort to evaluate the breastfeeding practices and knowledge of recently delivered mothers about breastfeeding practices. [1] This clinical article is a community-based cross-sectional study conducted among women who residing and delivered in the region of Uttar Pradesh (Moradabad), India. I truly appreciate the effort behind the authors' intention and would like to through some more light required in this holistic domain.

Mothers' own milk is the nature's gift representing a balanced diet to a neonate for healthy growth and development in addition to its myriads of benefits like preventing stunting, protecting against infectious and chronic diseases, and decreasing infant mortality. [2] Breastfeeding is a holistic approach immediately follows after birth of a new baby. It provides all the nutrients that a baby needs for the first six months of life to grow and nourish. It also provides high-quality nutrients and helps protect against infection up to two years of age or more. It protects babies from infections and illnesses, babies find breast milk easy to digest. In addition to these, breastfeeding promotes faster return to mother's pre-pregnancy weight, lowers the rate of breast and ovarian cancer in the mother, facilitates the emotional relationship or bonding between mother and baby. [2]

Breast milk is the perfect nutrition for babies, it is always clean and it is always available, it takes no preparation, it is always maintained at the correct temperature and easy to carry out compared to feeding formula. Irrespective of all these benefits and advantages some women may not wish to breastfed. [3] For such mothers, risks of not breastfeeding should be made educated. The risk of not breastfeeding includes babies may get sick more often with diarrhoea, malnutrition and pneumonia and are at increased risk of dying. And babies do not get natural protection to illnesses. Therefore, to evaluate the breastfeeding practices and awareness among delivered mothers the present study was undertaken. Similar to this Rajak et al in 2023 assessed the knowledge of mothers and others factors which contribute to breastfeeding practices. This study was a one-year hospital-based cross-sectional study conducted among 400 mothers who followed up with the hospital for the healthcare of their child, aged between six and 24 months. From these two surveys it is surprising that the levels of breastfeeding awareness and practice among mothers fell short of both national statistics and WHO recommendations. [4] Breast feeding also matters in neonates afflicted with cleft lip and palate [5-9]. It is essential that all mothers and care takers should have knowledge about this. Therefore, I would like to end this letter by concluding as 'it is highly essential to disseminate detailed information on breastfeeding in a community at large scale to enhance breastfeeding practices. Various effective measures like enhancing the current health care system and media promotion are mandatorily required to make stronger babies and future stronger individual for the growth of the nation.

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